

North Africa (Northern African) Research and Innovation Management Association (NARIMA) *initiative*

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Definition, Vision and Mission:

Definition: NARIMA initiative is a non-profit organization and framework which will act as a leading player in the research and innovation management of the North Africa region (Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco and Tunisia). It will provide a platform for the promotion and use of the best practices in research and innovation management through research and academic institutions in North Africa.

Mission: To foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and capacity building among research and innovation managers/authorities, stakeholders and their representatives in North Africa.

Accordingly, NARIMA brings together practitioners and stakeholders of research and innovation managers/authorities, stakeholders and their representatives for both higher education and research institutions

Vision: To be the leading platform for research and innovation management in North Africa. NARIMA focuses basically on the promotion and motivational actions that could enhance the performance of researchers and research managers and stakeholders in different science fields, higher education and research institutions in the northern African countries.

Moreover, NARIMA is predominantly acting as the research and innovation catalyst where it provides the research and higher education institutions in the North African region with full recommendations and opportunities for collaboration & partnership at the regional and international levels.

NARIMA initiative membership & partners & funders NARIMA initiative will be open to all interested candidates in innovation and S&T policies, strategies and management whether from Individuals or organizations. Later, other issues will be discussed as membership conditions, types, benefits, fees, etc.

NARIMA initiative will benefit from the progress made by other similar organizations like CARIMA (Central African Research and Innovation Management Association), SARIMA (Southern African

Research & Innovation Management Association) and WARIMA (West African Research and Innovation Management Association), where active collaboration with these networks and associations will be established.

NARIMA initiative will seek funding from all active potential concerning sponsors.

NARIMA initiative will have active collaboration and partnership with scientific influential international organizations as AAS, TWAS, *etc.*

Identifying Goals and Objectives:

Since, presently, scientific research and development for innovation play an important role in human life, with NARIMA, we aim that research institutions in North Africa will have the opportunity to reinforce R&I system with global standards and through networking on competitive bases by improving research management capacity and connecting research institutions through South-South and South-North collaborations.

Also, the organization will be an opportunity for North Africa experts to be more active and updated about new R&I approaches and will enhance the whole R&I environment in North Africa to be more productive and impactful for the sake of development. NARIMA is assisting higher education and research institutions to appropriately establish their strategy according to the national and/or regional socio-economic requirements.

Key goals and objectives :

1. Promote excellence in research and innovation management practices.
2. Enhance networking and collaboration among research and innovation professionals.
3. Support capacity building and professional development opportunities.
4. Advocate for policies that foster research and innovation in North Africa.

Each goal and objective will be measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound.

Conducting Stakeholder Analysis:

Through NARIMA, several tasks will be done as

1. Identifying key stakeholders, such as researchers, innovators, universities, research institutions, government agencies, industry representatives, and funding bodies.
1. Assessing their needs, interests, and expectations regarding research and innovation management.
2. Determining how the association can address and align with these stakeholders` needs.

Developing Strategies and Action Plans:

Based on the goals and objectives, strategies will be developed that outline the broad approaches to achieving them, such as:

1. Establishing a robust knowledge-sharing platform through conferences, seminars, and workshops.
 2. Facilitating networking opportunities through online communities, forums, and collaboration initiatives.
 3. Creating a resource center with best practices, case studies, and toolkits for research and innovation management.
 4. Collaborating with regional and international partners to access funding, expertise, and resources.
 5. Advocating for supportive policies and funding mechanisms at the national and regional levels.
 6. Promoting the professional & scientific development programs related to the 17 UN SDG.
 7. Develop detailed action plans for each strategy, including specific tasks, responsible parties, timelines, and resource requirements.
 8. Advancing best practices in research management and institutional administration:
 - i) Research governance and strategies;
 - ii) research policies, processes and procedures;
 - iii) institutional support services and infrastructure;
1. Promoting the integration of high professional skills in research management in the region's institutions.
 2. Increasing the innovation awareness and skills for researchers & research managers.
 3. Assessing the situation of R&I in North Africa specially for vital fields such as health, water, agriculture, energy and other disciplines to facilitate networking and collaboration.
 4. Identifying North African experts in the management of research and innovation.
 5. Developing specific programs of NARIMA initiative targeting constraints and opportunities for each country.
 6. Developing more technology-oriented training programs/platforms allowing access to more beneficiaries.
 7. Establishing regional research and innovation management forums for research managers/stakeholders.

Implementation and Monitoring:

The goals and aims of NARIMA will be implemented by :

1. Allocating resources, including finances, human capital, and infrastructure, to support the implementation of the action plans.
2. Establishing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess progress, identify challenges, and make necessary adjustments.
3. Regular communication and engagement with association members and stakeholders to gather feedback and ensure alignment with their evolving needs.

Sustainability and Growth:

NARIMA will develop strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability and growth of the association via:

1. Developing a membership structure with appropriate benefits and fees.
2. Seeking sponsorship and partnerships with industry and funding bodies.
3. Exploring revenue-generating opportunities, such as consulting services or training programs.
4. Expanding the association's reach by actively engaging with neighboring regions and international counterparts.

The high-level framework, and NARIMA strategic plan will depend on the unique context and available resources to the association.

This framework should be regularly reviewed and updated to stay relevant and responsive to the evolving needs of the research and innovation community in North Africa.

Founders & Leadership of NARIMA initiative

The following members from (Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco and Tunisia) have founded NARIMA initiative and acts as its advisory board member (AB-NARIMA). AB-NARIMA includes Prof. Amal Amin (Egypt), Dr. Abdelali Lammari (Morocco), Dr. Chemseddine Tidjani (Algeria), Prof. Haikel Jelassi (Tunisia), Prof. Haitham Sghaier (Tunisia) and Eng. Nabil Ksibi (Tunisia).

NARIMA was announced as an initiative until all lawful arrangements were ended to found NARIMA as an association with physical presence and headquarters.

First, NARIMA Egypt will be operated and it will be open for all NARIMA members for active participation.

NARIMA Initiative
Northern African Research and Innovation Management Association
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